

THE EFFECT OF SPECIMEN MACHINING PROCESSES ON FATIGUE LIFE OF 42CRMO4+QT STEEL

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The paper discusses the effect of various turning parameters setups on the fatigue strength of 8mm active diameter specimens manufactured from 42CrMo4+QT steel. In the search for the reasons for the varying fatigue strengths related to individual setups, the surface quality monitored in various surface roughness parameters and in residual stress values measured on the free surface is evaluated. However, the output of the analysis shows that these parameters are not sufficient and that neither each of them nor their combination can be related to the fatigue strengths of the output of the individual manufacturing setups.

Keywords: Fatigue strength, 42CrMo4, roughness effect, residual stress

INTRODUCTION

The research reported here was initiated once the first results of the large-scale FABEST project⁵ were evaluated [1]. This initial research focused on the size effect, the resulting paper had to conclude, however, that there are numerous other effects involved:

1. The roughness effect due to uneven cross sections of the specimens and thus also to the varying cutting speed limited by the available lathe.
2. Due to the high sensitivity of the turning conditions together with the bulk material microstructure the values and homogeneity of the surface residual stress state can differ.
3. The position of the surface of the active part of the specimen within the semi-product bar, which affects the local hardness of the material and thus also its fatigue response.

The first two items were clearly induced by the set of machining operations applied to manufacture the specimens. They would not be raised, had the recommendations of various standards been followed [2, 3] for fatigue testing of materials. The recommended practice is to test the specimens with prospective residual stresses ground away from the outer layer. The mechanical

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surface treatment should be followed then by polishing with the last polishing steps in the longitudinal direction. Within FABEST, however, we decided to prefer specimens closer to surface quality common in industrial applications, manufacturing of which is also less costly. The goal was set to deal with specimens with the arithmetic mean surface roughness $Ra = 0.8$.

The fact that the specimens with the smaller cross section cannot be manufactured by turning only due to the low cutting speed, and that a subsequent grinding must occur was one of the outputs of [1]. To keep the production of specimens economical and to study the various effects closer to the common production parameters, it was decided to focus on manufacturing the specimens with 8 mm active diameter, for which the common lathe of 4000 rpm can reach the cutting speed of 100 m/min. Some idea of what can be expected as regards the various machining setups was obtained thanks to the recent paper by Zielinski et al. [2], which hinted that such cutting speed could be acceptable as regards the surface quality.

The specific issue is residual stresses. The role of residual stresses during fatigue loading strongly depends on several factors, namely the mechanisms of fatigue crack initiation and damage. Unlike fatigue loading, which is dynamic and variable in its nature, residual stresses are static, so they alone do not contribute to the fatigue process itself. However, what is important is that residual stresses change the mean stress value of the fatigue load, which cannot be neglected. [3]

It is necessary to remark that the residual stress state is not only a macroscopic state, as usually presented, but a superposition of macro, micro, and submicroscopic. In Capek et al. [4], a comparison of macro- and microstresses with high-cycle fatigue life was made. A clear correlation was observed, where the tensile macroscopic residual stresses (RS) contributed to reducing the fatigue life. Significant changes of the microstresses after a high number of cycles were explained by the changes of dislocation layout and structure inside the material and grains as the first step of the fatigue crack initiation process.

Therefore, the study served to check various setups of the machining parameters of the turning operation, with the intention of avoiding a subsequent grinding phase. The paper shows how extremely this steel, which is so commonly used in more strength-demanding application, responds to various manufacturing setups.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Material, design of specimens

The material used to make the specimens is 42CrMo4+QT steel fabricated by TRINECKÉ ŽELEZÁRNÝ, a.s. and delivered from one heat No. T46157 in one batch to the CTU in Prague in a total quantity of 1.4 tons. It is the same heat used in other publications [1] or [5] related to the large-scale FABEST project. The semi-product is a rolled bar of 35mm in diameter provided in the form of 6m long bars. The static material tests of this batch of steel provided the tensile strength of 1097 MPa and the yield strength of 1001.5 MPa.

The microstructure of 42CrMo4+QT was analyzed by light optical microscope (LOM) Neophot32 equipped with a CCD camera and analytical software Nis Elements AR. For detailed observation, the scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM-7600F was used. The metallographic specimens were prepared by grinding the specimen using SiC papers up to P4000, prepolishing with 3 μ m diamond suspension and final polishing with colloidal SiO₂. To reveal the microstructure, the specimens were etched with 2% Nital (2 ml HNO₃ + 98 ml ethanol). The microstructure corresponds

to the quenched and tempered material. Prior austenitic grains ($\sim 20\text{-}25\ \mu\text{m}$) can be observed together with tempered lath martensite with lowered acicularity (see Fig. 1a), lower fraction of homogeneous bainite, minimum residual austenite and MnS based inclusions. Detailed analysis (see Fig. 1b) showed a uniform distribution of fine globular and partially elongated Fe_3C carbides across the martensitic/bainitic blocks and along the martensitic laths. The microstructure is uniform in the cross section of the bar.

FIGURE 1 42CrMo4+QT microstructure: (left) LOM micrograph; (right) SEM micrograph.

The first attempts to analyze the fatigue response of specimens with an hourglass design were made on specimens A03 (see, e.g., in [1]), which were derived from a recommendation issued by the manufacturer of the test machine used, see Fig. 2a. A slightly modified design was adopted for later specimens to conform to the ASTM standard [6], Fig. 2b. Both designs feature the hourglass design to prevent dangerous undercuts between the fillet radii and the cylindrical central section, and the threaded heads with M16x1 threads necessary for the transmission of the load from the testing machine.

FIGURE 2 Drawings of the specimen geometries: (a) A03 series; (b) A25 – A37 series.

The specimens treated in this paper were manufactured in three different phases:

1. Phase 0: Series A03 was manufactured as one of the first from the delivered material without realizing that the machining setup could affect the fatigue response extremely.
2. Phase 1: Series A25 – A29, the first five sets of turning parameters proposed by the VSB workshop.

3. Phase 2: Series A35 – A37, three sets of turning parameters proposed by the CTU.

In all cases, 10 specimens were prepared using the defined turning setup in Table 1 and they were used for the fatigue experiment. The only exception is the case A29, where 16 specimens were available for testing.

Machining parameters

As noted above, the setup used in the production of A03 specimens was chosen primarily based on economic production aspects. From the beginning, it was envisaged that a right machining setup should allow one to reach the desired surface quality with $Ra = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$ by turning only to minimise production costs and achieve the roughness relatively typical of engineering problems. When these specimens were received from the manufacturer, it was found that the desired roughness was not met at all, and a subsequent step of manual grinding was followed to achieve it. This step was forbidden in all subsequent phases and even higher roughness values than requested were accepted to see the overall fatigue response to different sets of machining parameters.

All specimens were manufactured on a DMG Mori NLX 2500MC/700 machine. In all cases, the rough cuts were done with the Decocut 1040 process fluid used, while the cut height was of 0.5 mm. Tooling equipment concerned the insert holder C4-PDJNR-27055-15HP and the inserts DNMG 15 06 08-MM 1125 (nose radius of 0.8 mm) or DNMG 15 06 04-SM 1125 (nose radius of 0.4 mm) of Sandvik Coromant. The different setups of the machining parameters are described in Table 1. What differed above all in Phase 1 was the cutting speed, which varied between 62.8 m/min and 100.5 m/min at the smallest diameter of specimens (which is also the hot spot of specimens), the feed rate, and the last cut height. The last three cuts in all cases of Phase 1 were summed up to 0.3 mm.

TABLE 1 Turning parameters of turning for individual evaluated variants of production.

Parameter		Series								
		A03	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A35	A36	A37
Cutting speed at min. D	v_c [m/min]	100.5	75	75.4	100	62.8	75.4	100	100	100
Spindle speed	[rot/min]	4000	2984	3000	3979	2500	3000	3979	3979	3979
Feed rate	F [mm/rev]	0.1	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.05	0.05	0.05
Process fluid		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Cooling fluid (last cuts)		x	x		x			x	x	x
Cutter nose radius	R [mm]	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.4	0.4
Last cut height	h_1 [mm]	0.1	0.05	0.1	0.1	0.05	0.1	0.1	0.05	0.1
Second-last cut height	h_2 [mm]	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.15	0.2
Third-last cut height	h_3 [mm]	0.5	0.15	0.1	0.1	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.2
Roughing cut height	h_R [mm]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

Based on the article by Zielinski et al. [2], and based on the fatigue performance of Phase 1, Phase 2 featured the highest possible cutting speed of 100 m/min, but differed above all in the radius of the cutter nose (0.8 mm in the case of A35), and in the setup of heights of the last three cuts. These were chosen to achieve the total height of the last three cuts of 0.5 mm, expecting that this could remove a deeper layer of material presumably too affected by residual stresses by the preceding roughing phase.

Roughness measurements

Roughness was measured in two different universities. The measurements at the CTU in Prague used the Mahr mechanic profilometer MarSurf LD 120 contour and roughness measurement station, while the measurements from Mondragon University are based on Mitutoyo SurfTest SJ-210. This is not the only difference. In the case of measurements on Mahr, the total length equal to 5 wavelengths set from the R_{sm} measurements were analyzed along one path orientated longitudinally in the position of the active diameter of the specimen (the hot spot, where the fatigue cracking probably should occur). In addition to that, one more path slightly overlapping but out of the central position was evaluated, to see if there are some specific differences in these two locations, while the hot-spot output was deemed more critical.

In Mondragon, the profile was measured at six equidistant locations in the central part of each sample (60° apart) according to the ISO 4287 standard. The mean value of the R_a and R_z parameter reported for each specimen in Tables 2 and 3 were calculated from the six measurements for statistical representativeness.

State of residual stress

For each series, at least two analyses of macroscopic residual stress were performed. The measurements at the CTU in Prague were performed during the slow rotation of the specimen, so results from the entire perimeter were monitored and thus the final stated values are, in fact, averaged along the perimeter.

Lattice deformations of the diffraction lines $K\alpha_1$ of the planes $\{211\}$ of the ferrite phase were analyzed using the X'Pert Pro MPD diffractometer with chromium radiation. The diffraction angles $2\theta^{hkl}$ were determined by using the Pearson VII function and the Rachinger method. Standard X-ray elastic constants $\frac{1}{2}s_2 = 5.76 \text{ TPa}^{-1}$, $s_1 = -1.25 \text{ TPa}^{-1}$, and the $\sin^2\psi$ method were used to calculate the state of residual stress. The irradiated volume was defined by the geometry of the experiment, the rotation of the specimens, the effective penetration depth of the X-ray radiation (approx. $5 \mu\text{m}$), and the pinhole size ($0.25 \times 0.3 \text{ mm}^2$).

Fatigue tests

Fatigue tests were carried out using the Amsler HFP422 resonator, which operates close to the resonance frequency of the machine-specimen setup. For one specific specimen design used for all tests in the campaign, the load frequency does not change significantly due the applied load level or due to the induced elongation, as it is common otherwise if using hydraulic testing machines. In this case, the frequency of the setup was approximately in the range of 152-154 Hz.

Test cases were run with the load ratio -1 in fully reversed push-pull loading. The end of each test was marked either by the obvious rupture of the specimen or by exceeding one of the criteria:

- Frequency drops by 5 Hz (Series 0), 22 Hz (Series 1 and 2).
- The load amplitude changes by $\pm 0.2 \text{ kN}$ (Series 0), $\pm 0.5 \text{ kN}$ (Series 1 and 2).
- Mean load changes by $\pm 0.5 \text{ kN}$ (all series).
- $2 \cdot 10^7$ cycles are reached. These specimens are classified as run-outs. No run-out was reached, except for one case in the A29 configuration.

RESULTS

Roughness values

The roughness values achieved are shown in Table 2 for the R_a parameter and in Table 3 for the R_z parameter. The reported values are shown for two or three specimens per series, and measurements were made with two different machines.

TABLE 2 Roughness R_a values measured on specimens. Note: * roughness values affected by manual grinding. In all other cases, the last surface-modifying process was turning.

	Spec. No.	R_a [mm]								
		A03*	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A35	A36	A37
Mondragon, Mitutoyo	1		1.44	0.86	0.92	0.96	0.62	0.86	1.30	1.28
	2		0.78	0.49	1.18	1.14	0.69	0.88	1.21	1.21
	11		2.61	0.37	0.99	0.85	0.62	0.95	1.08	1.30
	Mean		1.61	0.57	1.03	0.98	0.65	0.89	1.20	1.26
CTU, Mahr	1	0.69	1.30	0.97	1.06	1.61	0.60	0.60	1.04	1.17
	2	0.54	0.82	0.31	1.39	2.00	0.69	0.55	0.82	1.00
	3							1.01	0.85	1.17
	Mean	0.61	1.06	0.64	1.22	1.81	0.64	0.72	0.90	1.11

As mentioned in the captions of Tables 2 and 3, the A03 series cannot be evaluated in the same way as regards the effect of turning setup on the final roughness quality, because its production included the final manual grinding phase. The achieved roughness values show a too large scatter of values for the A25 and A26 setups, which is visible in both the R_a and R_z values. The chosen manufacturing conditions apparently do not lead to stable production quality. This is even though the A26 setup leads to ones of the lowest roughness values observed in the scope of tests.

TABLE 3 Roughness R_z values measured on specimens. Note: * roughness values affected by manual grinding. In all other cases, the last surface-modifying process was turning.

	Spec. No.	R_z [mm]								
		A03*	A25	A26	A27	A28	A29	A35	A36	A37
Mondragon, Mitutoyo	1		7.44	4.63	4.13	5.03	3.00	5.25	7.31	8.03
	2		4.16	2.54	5.11	5.80	2.84	5.10	7.52	7.03
	11		9.74	2.01	4.46	4.00	3.36	4.67	6.47	7.75
	Mean		7.11	3.06	4.57	4.94	3.07	5.01	7.10	7.60
CTU, Mahr	1	4.63	6.88	5.27	5.05	8.01	2.88	3.63	6.19	6.69
	2	4.50	4.33	1.99	5.55	9.08	3.35	2.81	4.40	5.67
	3							5.66	5.62	6.69
	Mean	4.56	5.61	3.63	5.30	8.54	3.12	4.03	5.40	6.35

Surprising is the difference in values measured in Mondragon and at the CTU in the case of A28 specimens: the magnitude of values substantially differs (although the relative difference between roughness values of specimens 1 and 2 is similar). The reason for this discrepancy may be the different ways the measured signals were processed. While at the CTU one measured length of five wavelengths is reported in the middle section of the specimen, Mondragon measurements averaged results of three such measurements in the middle section and of three other measurements more to the side. In the case of A28 specimens, the additional measurements done at the CTU more to the side show much lower roughness values not far away from the central position. If such values are included in the averaging, they must lead to lower final roughness values, as reported here. In other cases of Phase 1 specimens, so pronounced differences based on the longitudinal position of the measured length were not observed.

The stablest and lowest roughness values are achieved with the A29 setup. All the setups proposed in Phase 2 (series A35-A37) perform quite poorly in terms of the roughness achieved, and only series A35 could be considered close to the desired values of $Ra = 0.8 \mu\text{m}$.

Residual stresses

Residual stress values provided in Table 4 are the result of a post-processing of individual measurements, which end up with minimum and maximum achieved residual stresses in each direction, measured on n specimens. This means that the first value in the $X \pm Y$ record is a mean value of *the* minimum and maximum values n times for every measured specimen. It is not a mean value by itself. The Y -value in this record is then half of the span between these minimum and maximum values of the given configuration.

In the case of the A03 experiments, residual stress measurements were performed only after constant amplitude load-controlled fatigue tests were completed, leading to lifetimes exceeding 1 million cycles in both cases. Despite the number of cycles reached, and to decrease the potential effect of the preceding cyclic loading, measurements were not performed at the hot-spot location (where the cracking occurred), which could be, additionally, the area most affected by plastic response. In the case of A03 (and nowhere else), the measuring position was set 8 mm away from the minimum diameter, where the local stresses during the cyclic loading should be substantially smaller. In all other cases, the minimum diameter location was targeted in these measurements.

Within Table 4, the results are expected to describe the overall residual stress levels well owing to the measurement setup that gathers the response throughout the perimeter. If these values are mutually compared, quite pronounced differences in residual stresses can be observed, reaching values from -490 MPa in compression (A03 setup) to 442 MPa in tension (A27 setup), both in the axial direction. From these reported values, the configurations A26, A35, and A36 seem to invoke the residual stresses closest to zero. The directional effect is evident, where there are higher residual tensile stresses in the axial direction and lower in the tangential direction. The only exception is the A28 setup, where the induced stress field is the closest to the equibiaxial stress state despite quite pronounced values.

From the achieved axial residual stresses, the fatigue-beneficial ones are those related to A03 configuration above all (while the compressive stresses are of such a high level that it might be assumed that it could already worsen the fatigue response by being of a too high magnitude). The only other pronounced compressive axial residual stresses are found for the A37 series, where the scatter band is so large, however, that the measured residual stress values vary between zero and approximately -350 MPa. This series shows the largest scatter of measured residual stresses from all

configurations, and thus it can be assumed that the output quality of the manufacturing process is not stable enough. A bit lower scatter (but around nearly zero central value) can also be detected for the A35 configuration.

TABLE 4 Results of the macroscopic residual stresses. Note: * In the case of A03 experiments, the values were obtained after the fatigue tests were finalised. They relate to the location 8 mm away from the minimum diameter, which should be minimally affected by the preceding loading.

Series	CTU in Prague		
	<i>n</i> of spec.	axial	tangential
A03*	2	-490±81	-340±39
A25	2	102±42	-17±60
A26	2	55±61	102±116
A27	2	442±35	113±40
A28	2	222±42	-62±53
A29	2	207±23	184±109
A35	3	-36±114	-60±59
A36	3	43±69	49±77
A37	3	-184±168	-76±85

Fatigue strengths

The fatigue response achieved is shown in two graphs in Figs. 3 and 4. The series related to the machining setups Axx are described as fatigue curves FABxx. Except for the data points related to each configuration, fatigue curves derived from the regression by the Kohout-Věchet curve [7]:

$$\sigma_a = a \left[C \cdot \frac{N+B}{N+C} \right]^\beta \tag{1}$$

are also depicted. This formula is promising in capturing the fatigue trend when it transcends from the common power-law region in the limited lifetime domain to the domain of the conventional fatigue limit.

Fig. 3 refers to the results of Phase 0 (A03 series unaffected by any attempts to improve fatigue response, but manually ground to reach the requested roughness) and from Phase 1 (series A25 – A29). Had there not been the available residual stress measurements (see Table 4) and showed extreme compressive residual stresses of the A03 configuration, the output would be hard to explain. The performance of the A03 series is clearly the best from the observed series in Fig. 3.

If the performance of specimens in Phase 1 is assessed, the fatigue curves related to A27, A29, and A25 perform better than A26 and A28. The obvious worst output is obtained from the setup related to A28, and the reason for its low performance seems to be the lowest cutting speed for all combinations. The second worst setup in the fatigue response obtained is the curve related to the A26 setup. In the machining setup, it has the same cut area (0.05 mm x 0.1 mm) as A28 although the sides are transposed, but it features a higher cutting speed. This could be the reason for the lower roughness values and the lower residual stresses achieved, which allow the fatigue response to reach better values. It can be hypothesised that a specific cutting speed is required to achieve adequate formation of the chip without inducing unnecessary plastic deformation and consequent residual stresses.

The rest of Phase 1 curves are quite similar in response. The worse output of A25 above 1 million cycles is caused by a single experimental data point, which distinctly affects the position of the fatigue curve close to its position, because it is close to the border of the interpolated area. The scatter of data points of the A25 fatigue curve is significantly higher than those of the rest of the curves except for A26. This aspect is likely related to the scatter of roughness values measured and presented in Tables 2 and 3, which was commented on previously.

FIGURE 3 S-N curves of specimens from series A03 to A29.

Taking into account the high residual tensile stresses caused by the A27 setup, it is surprising that it reaches the best fatigue output from the Phase 1 experiments. A29 is only slightly worse, contradicting the better roughness values and lower residual stresses of this combination compared to A27. The position of the FAB29 curve is significantly affected by the scatter of data points, which is twice the standard deviation of stresses compared to the FAB27 curve. Both residual stress measurements and roughness measurements in the case of the variant A29 are very homogeneous, but this curve is composed of 16 data points compared to 10 data points of the other variants. That means that the specimens analyzed on roughness and residual stresses could be less significant and it need not uncover the frequent outliers.

An interesting finding from experiments in Phases 0 and 1 can be detected from Fig. 3. Above the stress amplitude of 600 MPa, the effect of residual stresses is erased to such an extent that the curves overlap despite of the fact that the yield strength of this batch of QT steel is 1003 MPa. The regression curves in this position are usually driven by one or two data points only, so the remaining potential effect, the surface roughness effect, cannot be evaluated from these observations.

The results of Phase 1 led us to the assumption that the roughness values and residual stress values directly on the surface need not be descriptive enough to be related to the fatigue performance

observed. It was assumed the key undocumented difference could be the residual stress profile below the surface, and that it could be caused by too shallow final cuts, which removed a part of the residual stress profile beneath the surface, thus exposing at the surface the domain of the high tensile stresses, which would otherwise be found deeper below the roughened surface. Compared to the total depth of 0.3 mm removed by the last three finishing cuts in the Phase 1 specimens, Phase 2 designs were proposed to remove 0.5 mm by finishing cuts. Based also on the research by Zielinski et al. [2], it was decided to keep the cutting speed at 100 m/min, which relates to the spindle speed of 4000 rpm for the smallest diameter of the specimen.

FIGURE 4 S-N curves of specimens from the best performing series from Phases 0, 1 and Phase 2.

The proposed changes in the turning setup helped to some point apparently, see Fig. 4, where also the best performing setups A03 from Phase 0 and A27 and A29 from Phase 1 are shown. All new 3 fatigue curves reach higher lifetimes than the Phase 1 setups. It is obvious, however, that the regression curves above all in the case of A35 and A36 setups apparently neglect some of the lower lying data points. This is because the cracks started to appear out of the active section in those cases – they were initiated at the threads used for gripping the specimen. Because of that, the highest-lying fatigue curve related to the A35 setup is based on five data points only (all other five data points relate to the initiation at the threads). From these 5 data points accepted for the regression analysis, even two rightmost are still related to the cracks in the threads, i.e., out of the active cross section. They are accepted to show the trend in this region, while expecting the failure at hot-spot area would shift the curve in this area even more to the right. It is interesting to mention that these issues did not occur in the case of the A03 setup, although the fatigue performance of both cases is very similar.

In the case of A35 curve in Fig. 4, the unusual trend in the curve shape could cast some doubts. This is however a simple outcome of running the regression analysis with the S-type curve with two

horizontal asymptotes in the quasi-static and fatigue limit domains through a limited set of data points, where the importance of any of them is too high and can cause the curve to deviate from expectations. Because the curve A35 is based on 5 valid points only, it is obvious that the exact shape of the fatigue curve cannot be expected and it reflects rather the qualitative information on its potential position in the S-N space.

The order of curves from Phase 2 corresponds to the differences in the roughness values (though the difference in roughness values between A36 and A37 is negligible), but there is no specific explanation for why the setup related to A37 should lead to the worst fatigue response from Phase 2, if the residual stress values are analyzed.

DISCUSSION

Fatigue response to roughness and residual stress

Comparison of some of the fatigue curves presented in Figs. 3 and 4 shows that neither the information on residual stresses directly on the surface nor the information on surface roughness is sufficient to find the correlation between any or both of them with the fatigue life. The positions of FAB003 and FAB035 curves are only one of the examples of the unexpected response that can be found under a careful scrutiny.

This specific case clearly highlights that the residual stresses on the surface are not sufficient. The same can be stated based on comparison of the FAB36 and FAB37 curves. They differ by more than 220 MPa in the measured residual stresses, but the significant shift of FAB37 from the position FAB36 goes in the opposite direction than would be anticipated. There are isolated data points of the FAB36 set, which fall close to the trend of the FAB37 fatigue curve, but these are related not to some specimens of weaker quality (theoretically similar to the FAB37 response), but to cases where the cracks started in threads on the gripping heads of specimens.

The comparison of FAB36 and FAB37 curves is also interesting due to the very similar roughness characteristics in both cases. Therefore, the contradictory fatigue response of this duo thus must be assigned to a property which was not analyzed in the previous sections.

There is a common expectation that the average roughness parameter Ra is not adequate for correlating the roughness with the fatigue life. This is the reason why the FKM Guideline [8] proposes that its roughness factor is based on *the roughness* Rz , which emphasises the role of the largest extremes, while the average roughness focusses more on the general response. Logically, fatigue damage is the weak link mechanism, and Rz could be more related to the fatigue life of the output, when a specific large surface abnormality can trigger crack initiation. Despite that, the comparison of Tables 2 and 3 shows that there are no substantial differences in the ranking of individual series if both roughness parameters are compared.

These days, it is more frequently highlighted that the mechanical roughness measurement by a stylus along a line need not represent the complexity of the roughness characteristics [9], and that areal parameters obtained from microscopes optically could be more promising. In this case, however, the surface characteristics are fully defined by turning operation only (except of A03 case). This leads to the well-defined periodic pattern that can be described in the cylindrical coordinate system. There are no extensive features that would not be oriented circumferentially as, e.g., manual grinding could invoke. Because of that, it is not expected that the areal surface roughness parameters could bring adequate improvement here.

Potential nontreated factors

The apparent mentioned but not evaluated factor which could better correlate with the fatigue life obtained is the residual stress profile beneath the surface. The attempt to minimise it was envisaged while preparing Phase 2. The residual stress profile induced below the surface by the roughing cuts was requested to be removed by a multiple of cuts running altogether deeper (0.5 mm), than in Phase 1 (0.3 mm altogether). However, it is questionable if one expects that significant residual stresses invoked by any turning operation can be found deeper than about 0.1 mm deep – Zielinski et al. refer to reach the negligible residual stress near 0.07 mm depth. Then the question is whether the comparatively better results of Phase 2 cases are not caused rather by the higher cutting speed (100 m/min), which only A27 from Phase 1 achieves.

If these cases are compared in Fig. 5 as regards the area cut away in each turn, while the same high cutting speed makes the cases of A27, A35, A36 and A37 comparable, the lower cut height of the very last cut (A35 and A36) seems more promising. The fatigue curve of the A36 case with the smallest cut area is specific in the highest scatter of data points, which no other fatigue curve from the observed scenarios exceeds. It is hypothesised that the small area cut away with the more inclined cutting force on the side can cause the cutting tool to vibrate if it encounters harder microstructural constituents. Consequently, this might result in less repeatable quality of the final specimens. If this theory were to be right, the setup depicted in A28 case of Fig. 5, but with a cutting speed of 100 m/min, could be very interesting.

The case of the A03 setup was evaluated if the high compressive residual stresses are not accompanied by some specific microstructural changes near the surface. This question was raised based on the research done, e.g., by Forsyth [10], proving that some operations (drilling in his case) can cause significant microstructural transformation, which can delay fatigue damage. No traces of such modifications were found.

FIGURE 5 Graphical comparison of areas cut away at every turn based on the request cutting conditions for individual setups.

CONCLUSIONS

The article summarises the status quo of research on optimal turning parameters for specimens with 8 mm active diameter made from 42CrMo4+QT, if subsequent grinding operations are not desired. It shows how tremendous the effect of the machining setup on the final fatigue strength can be while the fatigue strength at 1 million cycles ranges from 360 MPa to 510 MPa. This result is reached despite the relatively narrow band of achieved roughness, which is usually the only measure checked at the output check after manufacturing.

The problem found in our analysis is that neither surface roughness nor residual stress values obtained on the surface are correlated with the fatigue strengths or fatigue life achieved. This finding

asks for a check of other effects that could drive the onset and growth of fatigue cracks but were not analyzed here, namely the residual stress profile in the direction towards the depth from the surface and microstresses analyses. As such characteristics are demanding to achieve in practical situation (post-production check), the output is blank – the worst achieved fatigue strength must be used in fatigue life estimations and the vast space above it (measuring nearly one half of its value) cannot be effectively used unless a detection method of still unknown parameter affecting the final fatigue life is found.

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